

Fuzzy Based Problem-Solution Data Structure as a Data Oriented Model for ABS Controlling

Ahmad Habibizad Navin, Mehdi Naghian Fesharaki, Mohamad Teshnelab, and Ehsan Shahamatnia

Abstract—The anti-lock braking systems installed on vehicles for safe and effective braking, are high-order nonlinear and time-variant. Using fuzzy logic controllers increase efficiency of such systems, but impose a high computational complexity as well. The main concept introduced by this paper is reducing computational complexity of fuzzy controllers by deploying problem-solution data structure. Unlike conventional methods that are based on calculations, this approach is based on data oriented modeling.

Keywords—ABS, Fuzzy controller, PSDS, Time-Memory trade off, Data oriented modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

ANTI LOCK braking system (ABS) is now a common feature on most vehicles. It was first developed in 1950s for aircrafts, but then was too expensive for road vehicles. The first ABS for vehicles appeared in the late 1960s. Although it was commercially unsuccessful, the associated researches fostered a number of other commercial products [2]. Since then, ingenious mechanical ABSs have been developed, but the real growth in ABS technology was made possible by the invention of integrated electronics and microcomputers in 1970s. As a result ABS controllers have moved inevitably to microcomputer based methods [2].

When braking force is applied to a rolling wheel, it will begin to slip. In a normal driving condition the vehicle velocity is almost the same as the wheel velocity, but If braking force is applied, these two velocities will be different. Slip is defined as the difference between the vehicle velocity, V_{veh} and the wheel circumferential velocity, V_{whl} normalized to the vehicle velocity, and denoted by λ :

$$\lambda = \frac{V_{veh} - V_{whl}}{V_{veh}}$$

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A. Habibizad Navin is with the Computer Engineering Department of Islamic Azad University of Tabriz, Iran. He is also collaborating with the IAUT Computer Research Laboratories, CRL. (phone: +98-914 412 5973; fax: +98-411-3320725; e-mail: ManHabibi@yahoo.com).

E. Shahamatnia is with the AI Department of Islamic Azad University of Qazvin, Iran. He is a member of ACM and *Young Researchers Club*. (e-mail: E.Shahamatnia@ACM.org).

M. Naghian Fesharaki is with the Computer Department of Islamic Azad University, Science and Research Branch, Tehran, Iran.

M. Teshnelab is with the Computer Department of Islamic Azad University, Science and Research Branch, Tehran, Iran.

If sufficient braking force is applied, the wheel will “lock up”, that is, slide without turning at all. During the wheel lockup, vehicle greatly loses steering control and the friction force which stops the vehicle is reduced. The braking wheel provides two-forces, the lateral force, F_L and the braking force, F_B as shown in Fig. 1. These two forces are induced from F_N , the weight of the vehicle. The first, F_L , provides the vehicle steering control and the lateral stability, while the second, F_B , provides the braking forces, which stop the vehicle. These forces are nonlinear function of slip [5], [6] as shown in Fig. 2.

The lateral force is greatest at the zero slip. When slip increase, the lateral force decrease, that is, the ability to steer and control the direction of the vehicle is decreased. The brake force is zero at zero slip, and it has a peak value when the slip is close to 0.2. Most control strategies define their performance goal as maintaining slip near a value of 0.2 throughout the braking trajectory. Because in this area the braking force is close to maximum and the lateral force is sufficiently large to providing the lateral stability.

Not only the braking force and the lateral force are nonlinear function of slip but also slip is nonlinearly related to many other factors, such as maximum road coefficient of friction, temperature of the brake lining, temperature of the brake fluid, pedal force, wearing of tire, initial speed of vehicle and etc. These factors are varying with time. This means braking system is a high-order nonlinear time variant system. Therefore there is no classical equation for braking system control. The knowledge base methods can be used for effective controlling of this system. [4] Uses neural network, [3] introduces fuzzy logic controller and [1] give an optimal fuzzy logic controller. The fuzzy logic controller is an effective controller for ABS but it has a high computing complexity. We use Problem-Solution Data Structure for almost removing this complexity.

II. FUZZY LOGIC CONTROLLER

Using fuzzy logic controllers for ABSs was introduced by D. P. Madau, et al, in 1993 [3]. It compromises two input variables; slip λ and wheel acceleration α , for generating the control output δu , which controls the force applied to the brake lining. It also has following five rules to drive the fuzzy logic kernel:

1. If λ is Pos. Small then δu is Pos. Small.
2. If α_{whl} is Neg. Large then δu is Neg. Med.
3. If α_{whl} is Pos. Large then δu is Pos. Large.
4. If λ is Pos. Large then δu is Neg. Large.
5. If λ is Pos. Medium then δu is Neg. Small.

The fuzzy logic kernel utilizes standard max-min fuzzy inference. The center of area method was used to generate the control output δu .

Another fuzzy logic controller for an ABS braking system appeared in 1995 [2]. It uses three input variables inferred from the road condition identifier, the current slip ratio GLISS, predicted slip ratio GLPRED and braking torque variable COUPLE. It also has four decision variables (blockage, ice, wet and dry) which only takes values zero or one. The following eleven rules drive its fuzzy logic kernel:

1. RULE DRY 1;
 IF DRY IS TRUE AND;
 GLPRED IS NOT VLARGE;
 THEN DGL IS LARGE;
 RULE-1;
2. RULE DRY 2;
 IF GLISS IS LARGE AND;
 DRY IS TRUE AND;
 COUPLE IS LARGE;
 THEN DGL IS MEDUM;
 RULE-2;
3. RULE DRY 3;
 IF GLISS IS SMALL AND;
 DRY IS TRUE AND;
 COUPLE IS LARGE AND;
 GLPRED IS NOT VLARGE;
 THEN DGL IS LARGE;
 RULE-3;
4. RULE DRY 4;
 IF GLISS IS MEDUM AND;
 DRY IS TRUE AND;
 GLPRED IS NOT VLARGE AND;
 COUPLE IS LARGE AND;
 THEN DGL IS LARGE;
 RULE-4;
5. RULE ICE 7;
 IF ICE IS TRUE AND;
 GLISS IS ZS AND;
 COUPLE IS ZS;
 THEN DGL IS ZS;
 RULE-7;
6. RULE ICE 5;
 IF GLISS IS ZERO AND;
 ICE IS TRUE;
 THEN DGL IS SMALL;
 RULE-5;
7. RULE ICE 8;

8. RULE BLOCKAGE;
 IF GLISS IS SMALL AND;
 ICE IS TRUE;
 THEN DGL IS ZERO;
 RULE-8;
9. RULE WET 10;
 IF WET IS TRUE AND;
 GLISS IS ZS AND;
 GLIPRED IS NOT LARGE
 THEN DGL IS SMALL;
 RULE-10;
10. RULE WET 11;
 IF WET IS TRUE AND;
 GLISS IS SMALL;
 THEN DGL IS ZS;
 RULE-11;
11. RULE WET 12;
 IF WET IS TRUE AND;
 GLISS IS ZERO AND;
 GLIPRED IS NOT LARGE;
 THEN DGL IS SMALL;
 RULE-12;

The output variable named “DGL”, represents the braking torque. Output defuzzification is performed by computing the centers of all minimum according to Mamdani’s method implemented in [2].

All fuzzy logic controllers determine the output in the following phases:

1. Input in mapped to the rules.
2. Each rule governs its output.
3. Output of rules determines the fuzzy output by fuzzy inference.
4. Defuzzify the output to real value befitting the engineering applications.

Fig. 1 Wheel forces
 F_N Normal Force, F_b Braking Force, F_l Lateral Force

Fig. 2 Brake force and lateral force are functions of slip

$$(\lambda_i, \alpha_i, \delta_i), i = 1, 2, \dots, 1600.$$

Fig. 3 Output of fuzzy controller

Each phase needs a considerable volume of computation. The computational complexity of a fuzzy controller is strongly related to the number of rules, membership function and their combinations, fuzzy inference and defuzzification method. For given rule sets above, the computational complexity of the second controller is higher than the first. Because it has eleven combined rules but the first one only has five simple rules.

We want to design fuzzy equivalent of the first controller which bears less computational complexity by using Problem-Solution Data Structure. It is explained in the next section.

III. PROBLEM - SOLUTION DATA STRUCTURE

Problem-Solution Data Structure, PSDS, is the arrangement of data in the memory. In other words PSDS is a database which stores the state of controller and solution of them, each component of PSDS has two segments: The first segment shows the problem, states of controller, and the second segment shows the solution, output of controller. We use PSDS in the following step:

1. Current state of controller is compared with the problems in the first segment of PSDS database and the nearest match is found.
2. The solution segment of the found match is use as the output of the controller.

Two fuzzy based PSDS controllers for controlling the ABS are introduced in the following sections.

IV. QUAN PSDS

We aim to design PSDS equivalent of fuzzy controller of [3], since it is a simple controller to implement. λ and α_{whl} are input variables for this controller and δ is the output. Fig. 3 shows the output, δ , in the input space.

The surface of Fig. 3 shows the output of controller for the giving input space. The quantization of this surface is given as subsurfaces, each of which represents a problem and its direct solution. This QUAN PSDS contains 1600 subsurfaces, each subsurface can be denoted by it's lower right corner as $(\lambda_i, \alpha_i, \delta_i)$. Then we can store the surface of Fig. 3 by 1600 subsurfaces as the form:

The (α_i, λ_i) identify the i -th problem and δ_i is the solution of it. Each subsurface makes one component of QUAN PSDS. For a given controller state (α, λ) , one subsurface $(\lambda_i, \alpha_i, \delta_i)$ exists such that (α, λ) settles in it. We index this subsurface by the function (1).

$$i = [\lambda] + (40 * [\alpha]) \quad (1)$$

Index of each subsurface is specified in the $\alpha - \lambda$ plan, as shown in figure 4. By this indexing, it is sufficient to store the δ_i instead of $(\lambda_i, \alpha_i, \delta_i)$, because index I is determined from equation 1 substituting (α_i, λ_i) . Therefore, QUAN PSDS was constructed by locating δ_i in the i -th memory location. This PSDS is similar to two dimensional table or array, Address of memory i denotes the problem and content of it determines the solution of this problem, which is used for ABS controlling in the following steps:

1. The controller state (α, λ) is read as the input, then index of problem, i , is calculated by the equation (1).
2. The output δ_i is retrieved from i -th memory location as the solution of problem which is assumed to be the output of controller.

Steps above are repeated during the lifetime of controller. This controller has a quantizing contradiction with the original fuzzy controller. But it is free of computing, and this contradiction is not important because the original controller is a fuzzy controller.

In this paper choosing the optimum quantization of subsurface is left as an open problem. This quantization must be in a way that PSDS controller will still remain stable and robust. Fig. 5 demonstrates the performance of fuzzy based PSDS controller and original fuzzy controller on the input space. These two controllers approximately have the same results.

In the next section we introduce another fuzzy based PSDS, named LINEAR PSDS for controlling of ABS.

1560	1561	1562	1563	1564	1565	1566	...	1595	1596	1597	1598	1599
1520	1521	1522	1523	1524	1525	1526	...	1555	1556	1557	1558	1559
1480	1481	1482	1483	1484	1485	1486	...	1515	1516	1517	1518	1519
1440	1441	1442	1443	1444	1445	1446	...	1475	1476	1477	1478	1479
1400	1401	1402	1403	1404	1405	1406	...	1435	1436	1437	1438	1439
1360	1361	1362	1363	1364	1365	1366	...	1395	1396	1397	1398	1399
...
...
...
...
160	161	162	163	164	165	166	...	195	196	197	198	199
120	121	122	123	124	125	126	...	155	156	157	158	159
80	81	82	83	84	85	86	...	115	116	117	118	119
40	41	42	43	44	45	46	...	75	76	77	78	79
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	...	35	36	37	38	39

Fig. 4 Index of each subsurface

Fig. 5 a) Output of fuzzy controller b) Output of QUAN PSDS controller

V. LINEAR PSDS

Similar to QUAN PSDS, LINEAR PSDS is constructed by the output of fuzzy controller of [3]. Fig. 6 shows the output of this controller with 16 subsurfaces. Each subsurface is denoted by its lower right corner $(\lambda_i, \alpha_i, \delta_i)$, slope at direction of λ , (γ_i) and slope at direction of α (θ_i) . That is to say each subsurface of Fig. 6 is identified by the vector $(\lambda, \alpha, \delta, \gamma, \theta)$. Then we can store surface of Fig. 6 by 16 subsurfaces as the form:

$$(\lambda_i, \alpha_i, \delta_i, \gamma_i, \theta_i), i=1, 2, 3, \dots, 16$$

The (α_i, λ_i) identifies the i -th problem and $(\delta_i, \gamma_i, \theta_i)$ is the solution of it.

Each subsurface constructs one component of LINEAR PSDS. For a given controller state, (α, λ) , one subsurface $(\lambda_i, \alpha_i, \delta_i, \gamma_i, \theta_i)$ exists such that (α, λ) settles in it. We index this subsurface by the function 2:

$$i = [\lambda \div 10] + 4 * [\alpha \div 10] \quad (2)$$

As shown in Fig. 7 index of each subsurface is written in their subsurface in the $\lambda - \alpha$ plan. By this indexing, it is sufficient to store $(\delta_i, \gamma_i, \theta_i)$ instead of $(\lambda_i, \alpha_i, \delta_i, \gamma_i, \theta_i)$, it is because index i is retrieved from equation (2) by substituting (α_i, λ_i) and vice versa. Therefore LINEAR PSDS is constructed by locating three memory locations starting from $3i$ respectively.

LINEAR PSDS is used for controlling ABS in the following steps:

1. The controller state (α, λ) is read as input. Then index of problem (i) is calculated, substituting (α, λ) in the equation (2).
2. Get three element from memory location $3i$ respectively as $(\delta_i, \gamma_i, \theta_i)$.

Fig. 6 Output of fuzzy controller

These three steps are repeated at the lifetime of controller.

Fig. 7 Index of each subsurface

Fig. 8 a) Output of fuzzy controller
 b) Output of LINEAR PSDS controller

3. The output of controller is calculated from linear adaptation function:

$$f(\alpha, \lambda) = \gamma_i(\alpha_i - \alpha) + \theta_i(\lambda_i - \lambda) + \delta_i \quad (3)$$

Fig. 8 shows the performance of fuzzy based LINEAR PSDS and the original the fuzzy controller. These controllers approximately have the same results; Because LINEAR PSDS controller has a linear contradiction with the original fuzzy controller.

VI. COMPARING

In this paper two methods, QUAN PSDS and LINEAR PSDS were introduce for ABS controlling. We can choose the

elements of any PSDS in a way that it operates the same results as the original fuzzy controller. PSDS controllers bear much less computational complexity compared with fuzzy controllers. Still two PSDS controllers introduced here, differ in memory consumption and computational complexity; QUAN PSDS uses 1600 but LINEAR PSDS uses 16 memory locations. LINEAR PSDS uses adaptation function to provide output, but QUAN PSDS gets output without any calculation. In the other word QUAN PSDS needs more memory locations, than LINEAR PSDS does, but it is faster than LINEAR PSDS.

VII. CONCLUSION

Fuzzy logic is an effective method using the knowledge for ABS controlling, but it suffers from the high computational complexity.

In this paper we introduced fuzzy based PSDS for ABS controlling. Unlike conventional calculation based methods, PSDS is an approach based on data oriented modeling which has proved to be in good conformity with computer structure and hence increase efficiency [7]. This method has the following advantages:

1. We get a fast fuzzy based controller.
2. If fast monitoring of V_{whl} is provided, then we will get a real time fuzzy based controller.
3. By using the PSDS method, input space is divided into subspaces. We can tune the output in each subsurface then we can get local optimization. Tuning δ_i in QUAN PSDS and $(\delta_i, \gamma_i, \theta_i)$ in LINEAR PSDS for getting local optimization is left as an open problem. This means we can optimize the fuzzy controller by PSDS method.
4. One of most important issues in ABS controlling is the prediction of maximum friction coefficient. This parameter can be predicted from sequence of much recently used PSDS elements (Sequence of controller states). This prediction by sequence of recently used PSDS elements is left as an open problem.

The PSDS is an infant method, it will grow and shine.

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